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Coordinator:

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WEBSITE:

<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/>

Nextfood - Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system

Practice Abstract #6: MSc. Agroecology course: Action learning in Farming and Food Systems

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During the introductory course of the Agroecology master program, the students dive into farming and food systems and try to facilitate change. Through the interactions with the real-life cases, the students develop not only knowledge about the systems, but more importantly they also develop the competences needed to engage with them. In addition to the case work, through various sessions and workshops, the students practice five core competences: observation, reflection, dialogue, visioning and participation. The goal is that by focusing on developing these competences, the students will become life-long learners who can contribute to facilitating improvements of farming and food systems in their future careers.

We believe that by focusing on developing competences rather than only knowledge, we can better equip the next generation of professionals for dealing with the complex issues of today's agrifood and forestry systems. There is little point in educating knowledgeable people if they are not able to use their knowledge for any good. And who doesn't want a competent and knowledgeable colleague? We therefore encourage stakeholders to appreciate and foster the focus on forming a competent generation of professionals.